

A Research Work on Information Gathering Tools

Arun S
PG scholar
Amal Jyothi College Of Engineering,Kanjirapally
Kottayam, Kerala.
Aruns2021@mca.ajce.in

Dr. Bijimol T K
Asst. Professor, Dept of Computer Science
Amal Jyothi College Of Engineering,Kanjirapally
Kottayam, Kerala
tkbijimol@amaljyothi.ac.in

Abstract— As we have done a detailed review/seminar on the base topic Dmitry is a KALI LINUX tool. The aim of these tools is to assist attackers in identifying information about a target and finding possible attack vectors that could be used against the device. This knowledge can be extremely useful in social engineering attacks because it provides the attacker with possible contact information. It can also make the perpetrator appear more trustworthy if they can include details about the owner's web page or domain. On the basis of preliminary research, we will compare Dmitry to other information gathering tools in Kali Linux, such as the Nmap tool, ZenMap, whois lookup, and SPARTA. Comparisons may be made based on the tools' different capabilities. Each tool has its own set of benefits. For example, Nmap is primarily used to discover hosts, ports, and services, as well as their versions, over a network, while whois lookup is primarily used to verify the availability of domain names and track down the registrants of fraud domains.

Keywords-Information Gathering, Kali Linux, Dmitry

I. INTRODUCTION

Dmitry is a component of the Kali Linux software's information collecting tool. These tools are designed to assist attackers in notifying information about a target as well as assisting them in identifying prospective attack pathways. This tool is excellent for locating information about the webpage's host and owner that is accessible via search engines.. These details can be extremely costly in social attacks because they provide the attacker with several points of contact, as well as the benefit of making the attacker appear more trustworthy if they can supply information about the web page or domain that the owner is using.

II. EASE OF USE

Dmitry is the name for a deep magic information gathering tool. It's a tool that comes with Kali Linux[1]. The purpose of this tool is to allow the user to acquire public information about the host. These can be used to collect a huge amount of costly pieces of information such as the:

- whois details of a host and it gives data or information about the domain which include name, address, and the contact information of the user which has registered in it.
- The net craft data for a target host. can include details such as the os ,web server release and time to time data of a web host.
- A search of email addresses that exist on the domain .
-

A transmission control protocol scan of the target to reveal any open ports and services running on the server.

III. HOW DMITRY IS USED

Dmitry may be found on Kali Linux's main menu, as well as by typing "Dmitry" into the command line to see the various options and help for the application. For this reason, Dmitry will be able to execute a command against a target in the format indicated below after it has been launched;[2]
Dmitry [flags] target

Break down the command and each of the options. Parameters which are kept are in square brackets are optional, and only needed if the user wants. The following flags are open to Dmitry:

- -o: This flag allows the user to define a file path to which the application's output should be written. The output will be written to the command line window if this parameter is not specified. This is the last parameter to be defined, and it must be followed by a file path.
- -i: This flag conducts a whois lookup on the target's IP address, and we'd like to do a whois lookup, so instead of using a domain name, we'd like to use the IP address.
- -w: This flag performs a whois lookup on the host address's domain name, so use it when you want to do a whois lookup but don't want to use the IP address..-n: This retrieves all Netcraft information for a given target host.
- -s: it searches for all of a target's subdomains.
- -e: it searches for all emails from a given domain.
- -p: the target is scanned for TCP ports.[2]

WHOIS against IP addresses and hostnames

The word "Who-is" refers to a protocol that runs on port TCP/43 and is used to query ownership databases for internet items such as domain names, autonomous systems, and internet protocol address block numbers, among other things.

IP addresses, contrary to popular belief, contain information about reverse pointer records, ownership, and a variety of other data (such as name servers) that can be accessed from WHOIS records. Which data is true depends on the owner of the IP range, and it is common to find correct information

that is incorrect.. Some cases it could also be treated as an historical information that can be used for competitive advantage in case of a company's attack surface reduction endeavors.

When DMitry is run with the flag "-i," it will query IP addresses for WHOIS information and, if a hostname is specified, it will resolve the matching A record. It will then query the server and display the results..

IV. HARVESTING SUBDOMAINS

As previously said, subdomain retrieval capability is an interesting function provided with this exploratory software. It searches the entire World Wide Web for probable hostnames within a specific registered name, which is enabled by using the "-s" parameter before the domain name:

Information collection entails acquiring several types of data on the target. It is the initial step or stage of Ethical Hacking[6], in which penetration testers or hackers (both black hat and white hat) attempt to obtain as much information about the target as possible in order to use it for hacking. To maximise the likelihood of a successful attack, we need to gather more information about the target in order to acquire more relevant outcomes. There are numerous tools that are similar to Dmitry, each with its own unique function.

NMAP vs ZenMAP

These two instruments are very useful. NMAP and ZenMAP are software used in Kali Linux for scanning during the Ethical Hacking process, and they are actually the same tool with the exception that the command line is used by NMAP, while the GUI is used by ZenMAP. NMAP is an excellent network discovery and security auditing tool. It comes in handy for tasks like network inventory management for many device and network administrators.

V. HOW IT FUNCTIONS

Step 1: Open nmap or zenmap from Applications 01-Information Gathering.

Stage 2 – The next step is to determine the OS type/version of the targeted host using NMAP's assistance; the OS type/version detection parameter is vector "-O."The command that we will use is –

```
nmap -O 192.168.1.101
```

Step 3 – Next step is, open the TCP and UDP ports and scan all the TCP ports based on NMAP[7].

nmap -p 1-65535 -T4 192.168.1.101 is the command we'll use.

The parameter "-p" means that all TCP ports are to be used. In this case, we're scanning all of the ports, and "-T4" specifies the scanning speed at which NMAP must operate.

VI. STEALTH SCAN

[4]Since it does not complete the TCP 3-way handshake, stealth scan is also known as half open scan. If an acknowledgement frame is received after a hacker sends a SYN packet to the destination target, it is presumed that the target has completed the link and the port is listening to it. If the target responds with a RST, the port is assumed to be closed or inactive.

nmap -sS -T4 192.168.1.101 is the command we'll use.

It's an open-source network scanner for reconfiguring and scanning networks. As a result, it's used to discover hosts, ports, and utilities, as well as their various variants, across a network. It then sends packets to the host, which it analyses in order to guide the desired effects. It may also be used to locate hosts., operating system detection, or scanning for open ports. It is one of the most popular reconnaissance tools.

Zenmap is a kali linux application that is used during the scanning process of ethical hacking[6]. It makes use of the graphical user interface (Graphical User Interface). This is an excellent programme for network discovery and security auditing. This performs the same tasks as the Nmap tool, or, to put it another way, it is the graphical interface variant of the Nmap tool. Zenmap makes use of a command-line interface.

It's a free network discovery and security auditing utility. Systems and network managers find tasks like network inventory, maintaining service update schedules, and tracking host or service uptime to be extremely useful.

VII. DISCUSSIONS

These are the same methods that are used to collect knowledge. The primary goal of the Dmitry tool is to extract knowledge about a destination target website. Nmap is a network discovery[5] and security auditing tool that is free and open source. Nmap is available in console and graphical versions for all major computer operating systems.. Nmap uses raw IP packets in novel ways to figure out what hosts are on the network, what services they provide (application name and version), what operating systems (and OS versions) they're running, what kind of packet filters/firewalls they're using, and a slew of other details. It's also useful for tasks like network inventory, controlling service update schedules, and tracking host or service uptime, according to many systems and network administrators. It was created to quickly search wide networks, but it also fits well with single hosts..

Unicorns can be an open source (GPL) platform that can help with data collection and security auditing.

It's an effort to build a User-end Distributed TCP/IP stack for data collection and interconnection.

Asynchronous stateless TCP scanning with all TCP flag variants, asynchronous stateless banner picking, and active/passive rogue scanning are among the scanner's features.. It provides a device scan that is scalable, accurate, and effective. Under the terms of the GPL licence, it is made available to the public for use. It offers a superior interface for delivering a stimulus to and measuring the response of TCP/IP activated devices. Dmitry (Deepmagic Information Gathering Tool) is a C-based UNIX/(GNU)Linux command-line programme. Dmitry has the ability to glean as much information as possible about a host. Subdomains, email addresses, uptime information, tcp port scans, whois lookups, and other information can be collected using the standard features.

VIII. CONCLUSIONS

Penetration testing is one of the most effective methods for determining the security of a system[3]. It has the ability to reliably assess the efficacy of security measures introduced on the device under review. With such a diverse range of supportive tools on the market, it can be difficult for clinicians to make well-informed decisions while searching for appropriate tools. By conducting an assessment on the performance of some specific tools, the study aims to provide the community with more credible references about the tools' effectiveness. The results of the experiment show that nmap is more efficient than the other tools because of its wide coverage, simple interface, quick response time, and high number of detected open ports. For a better penetration-testing experience, every penetration-tester (pen-tester) and hacker should master the art of information gathering. Analysts use this approach to figure out what consumers and users want. Techniques that provide collaborators with protection, utility, accessibility, learnability, and other benefits lead to greater cooperation, engagement, and honesty. Various tools and methods, including online sources such as Whois and nslookup, are available to assist hackers in gathering user information.

This phase is critical because it is necessary when conducting password guessing attacks (brute force) or other types of attacks on any target details (such as his pet name, best friend's name, age, or phone number).

IX. REFERENCES

- [1] Umesh TIMALSINA AND Kiran Gurung, Dmitry Framework with kali Linux, Department of Electronics and Computer Engineering, IOE, Thapathali Campus,Thapathali,Karthmandu,on March 10,2017.
- [2] W. Stallings (201)Dmitry and its uses (Prentice Hall)
- [3] Geer, D., and Harthorne, J. (2002). Penetration testing: a duet. In Computer Security Applications Conference, 2002. Proceedings. 18th Annual, pp. 185–195
- [4] P.D Meshram, Dr R.C Thool,Department of information Technology SGGSI&T Nanded ,offensive Security (2016). What is stealth scan,on 17 july 2015.
- [5]. Himanshu Sherwale, Sameer Patil, Vaibhav Deshmukh, and Pragya Singh, MS(Cyber laws and Information security) Division, Indian Institute of Information Technology, Allahabad, India, On March 2014.
- [6] Saleem, S.A. (2006). Ethical Hacking As a Risk Management Technique. In Proceedings of the 3rd Annual Conference on Information Security Curriculum Development, (New York, NY, USA: ACM), pp. 201–203
- [7] Wei Chen,Lead Security Researcher,Dmitry port scanning framework on 10/9/2018